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Design, manufacture and testing of 3D printed continuous fibre reinforced composite lug structures

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Introduction

Short Fibre Reinforced Composites 3D printing

Short carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (Harvard University)

Chopped carbon fibre reinforced nylon (MIT)

Short carbon fibre reinforced ABS (Taxes Tech University)

Short carbon fibre reinforced photo curable acrylic resin (Politecnico di Milano)

Short carbon fibre reinforced ABS (Oak Ridge National Laboratory and Boeing)

Introduction

Continuous Fibre Reinforced Composites 3D printing

Carbon fibre reinforced PLA
(Tokyo University of Science)

Markforged printer

Carbon fibre reinforced PLA
(Xi'an Jiaotong University, China)

3D printed bicycle lugs reinforced with continuous carbon fibre (Shpend Gerguri, 3D printing bicycle lugs reinforced with continuous carbon fibre. SAMPE UK&IRELAND, chapter 2016 Master class.)

Advantages and Challenges

Advantages:

- Complex structure
- Fast production
- Low cost for tooling
- Fibre steering

Challenges:

- Low mechanical properties
- Low TRL
- How to design fibre path
- New analytical method

Niche of application

Fokker Composites NH90 Trailing Arm

Composites and metal joining (Cranfield University)

Failure index distribution for the quasi-isotropic (QI) plate and the optimal variable stiffness (VS) plate

Fibre angle distribution for one ply

Aims of the project

- Develop a continuous fibre 3D printing technique
- Proposed application: key load carrying structures like joints and lugs
- New design concept: without cutting fibres in the existence of holes or notches
- Fibre paths design and optimization
- Sustain the specified loading conditions and achieve weight reduction

Ultimate Goal

CF-3DP development

Material development

- Carbon/PA6
- Commingled fibres
- $V_f \sim 55\%$

Commercial fibre filament

Pultruded commingled fibre filament

CF-3DP development

Printer development

- RepRap Velleman K8400
- Open-source
- Two nozzles
- Control printer using G-code

Velleman K8400

Coupon static testing – CF-3DP composites

Tensile Strength / MPa	Tensile Modulus / GPa	Compressive Strength / MPa	Compressive Modulus / GPa	Shear Strength / MPa	Shear Modulus / GPa
859.42	61.06	394.12	68.87	43.19	1.45

3D printed composite lug design – Initial design

Loading conditions: Pin load **tension** & Pin load **compression**

Suspension bridge

Arch bridge

Elena Sitnikova, Jun Chen, Jie Yang, Bintuan Wang and Shuguang Li. Conceptual design of braided preforms for the manufacturing of composite lug. Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Composite Materials, Xi'an, 20-25th August 2017.

3D printed composite lug design – Initial design

Pattern 1

Pattern -1

Pattern 2

Pattern -2

Pattern 3

Pattern -3

Overlap view of the 6 patterns

3D printed composite lug design – Initial design

3D printed composite lug design – Initial design

6 layers carbon fibre

6 layers glass fibre

6 patterns overlap view

3D printed composite lug design – Initial design

Number of layers	24
Thickness	~ 4mm
Layup sequence	$[1/3/1/2/-1/-3/-1/3/1/-2/-3/-1]_s$
Print time	~ 24h

	CFRP	Steel	Titanium
Thermal expansion coefficient	$0.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$10.1 \sim 17.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$8.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$

- ❖ One process for thermoplastic composites, multiple processes for metal
- ❖ Low volume, High value products
- ❖ Joints and lugs for wing and fuselage connection

Initial design - Finite Element Analysis

Rafael T. L. Ferreira, Ian A. Ashcroft, Shuguang Li, and Peng Zhuo

3D printed composite lug manufacturing - final design

1-1

1-2

1-3

2-1

2-2

2-3

3-1

3-2

4-1

4-2

3D printed composite lug manufacturing

32 layers layup sequence:

[4-1/3-1/1-3/4-2/2-1/3-2/4-1/1-2/2-2/4/2-3-3/1-1/4-1/2-3/3-2/4-2]_s

3D printed composite lug manufacturing

3D printed composite lug manufacturing – Benchmark laminate

32 layers layup sequence: $[+45/0/-45/90]_4s$

3D printed composite lug testing

Testing fixture design

Continuous fibre out-of-plane printing

Conclusions

- ❖ The continuous fibre 3D printing technique is developed.
- ❖ An open-source printer was modified for the printing process and a high fibre volume fraction commingled fibre tow was processed to be used as feed stock material.
- ❖ New design philosophy for key load carrying lug shape structure is proposed.
- ❖ A 32 layers lug shape samples were successfully manufactured and tested to validate the new design philosophy and to demonstrate the capability of the technology.
- ❖ Ultimate goal: aircraft wing joint

Thank you!